

DEPENDENCE OF THE COEFFICIENT OF LINEAR EXPANSION OF SOLIDS ON TEMPERATURE METROLOGICAL STANDARDIZATION IN MEASUREMENT

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Abstract: In order to determine whether the coefficient of linear expansion of solids depends on temperature, initially, various materials with clear standards are selected, and after determining their linear coefficient, other details are determined. For this purpose, the temperature dependence of the coefficients of linear expansion of brass, steel and glass is measured.

Key words: metrological standardization, thermal expansion, temperature, solid body, linear expansion.

To date, the increasing number of production enterprises and organizations in our republic leads to a decrease in the price of manufactured products and, moreover, to an increase in their quality. This increases the demand and attention to the quality indicators of the product. In recent years, as a result of the development of the automotive industry in our country, the localization of car spare parts has become one of the most important tasks, the standardization of car spare parts and the production of parts that meet the global demand [1-2]. As we know from the world experience, in the production of integral and spare parts of every car and in order to increase its service life, the standard conditions of details are checked and measured. Including thermal expansion of solid bodies, measurement of the coefficient of linear expansion of solid bodies as a function of temperature covers all areas of automotive engineering. The reason is that the verification of the uniqueness, use and durability of each detail has its effect on the quality of the manufactured product [3-4].

Taking into account that car parts are made of different solid materials, studying their linear expansion depending on temperature is one of the important tasks. Thermal expansion is the change in linear dimension of objects when they are heated. Different bodies expand differently from heat: in solids, the interaction between molecules and atoms (ions) is very strong, so heat expands less for solids, more for liquids, and more for gases. expressed by volume and linear expansion coefficients. The increase in volume of a body of a certain volume when it is heated by one degree is called the coefficient of volume expansion, and the increase in length of a body of a certain length when it is heated by one degree is called the coefficient of linear expansion. This coefficient changes with temperature changes. The coefficient of volume expansion of all liquids is approximately the same, equal to 1.273. Some bodies (water, cast iron, bismuth, etc.) shrink in size when heated to a certain temperature. For example, at 4° the volume of water is the smallest. Thermal expansion in this. is taken into account[5].

Measurement of the temperature dependence of the coefficient of linear expansion of solids is carried out under different conditions and with the help of laboratory equipment. In particular, the laboratory should be subjected to metrological inspection, otherwise it may have a negative effect on the result. In order to determine whether the coefficient of linear expansion of solids depends on temperature, initially, various materials with clear standards are selected, and after determining their linear coefficient, other details are determined. For this, measurements of the temperature dependence of the linear expansion coefficients of brass, steel and glass are carried out [6-8].

In testing these standards, a circulation thermostat is used to heat water, and heated water flows through pipes made of different materials. The rotary scale is used to measure the change in length as a function of temperature $\Delta s = s - s_0$ using a device consisting of 0.01 millimeter scale divisions [9-10]. The linear dependence

of the length s of the solid body on the temperature T

$$s = s_0 (1 + \alpha T) \quad (1)$$

where s_0 is the length at room temperature, T is the temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Coefficient of linear expansion of solids α is determined by their material.

It is possible to choose different solid materials when determining the linear expansion coefficient of solids as a function of temperature. For example, we can choose steel, brass, glass materials. Figure 1 shows a view of the laboratory equipment, a schematic view of the experimental equipment for measuring the linear expansion of heat-conducting pipes as a function of temperature, together with the expanding apparatus.

Figure 1

Here a- heat-conducting pipes, b- heat-conducting pipes, s - solid body under inspection, d- indicator (micrometer), e - adjuster, f- holder.

After measuring the initial temperature, set the room temperature to $T=0$. The circulation thermostat is connected and its temperature is set to 5°C higher than $T=0$. Wait until the thermodynamic equilibrium is established. After measuring the temperature T , the reading of the dial indicator is recorded. T increases the temperature in steps of approximately 5°C up to 100°C . This gives an opportunity to experimentally measure the dependence of the coefficient of linear expansion of various solids on temperature.

Table 1. Measured length change values Δs as a function of temperature T

brass		Steel		glass	
$\theta, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta s, \text{mm}$	$\theta, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta s, \text{mm}$	$\theta, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta s, \text{mm}$
20.0	0.03	24.1	0.07	30.4	0.02
25.0	0.09	26.0	0.09	39.9	0.04
30.0	0.13	30.5	0.12	49.9	0.05
35.0	0.18	34.1	0.15	60.3	0.08
40.0	0.24	40.7	0.20	70.3	0.09
45.0	0.30	44.3	0.22	79.9	0.11
50.0	0.35	49.7	0.26	90.5	0.12
57.0	0.41	52.7	0.28	98.9	0.15
59.8	0.46	62.8	0.35	-	-
64.0	0.50	66.8	0.38	-	-
70.0	0.55	69.1	0.39	-	-
75.0	0.60	72.9	0.42	-	-
80.0	0.67	76.8	0.45	-	-
85.0	0.71	80.1	0.47	-	-
90.0	0.77	84.9	0.51	-	-
95.0	0.82	89.6	0.55	-	-
99.8	0.86	92.8	0.56	-	-
-	-	98.6	0.60	-	-

To determine the coefficient of linear expansion as a function of temperature θ , a graph is made based on the measurement of the change in length Δs (Fig. 2). can be obtained for: $s - s_0 = s_0 \cdot \alpha \cdot T$

$$\Delta s = kT, \tag{2}$$

where $k = s_0 \cdot \alpha$. Equation (2) gives a linear approximation to the measured results a (Fig. 2).

Figure 2

The results are presented in Table 2. Table 2. Linear expansion coefficients a determined according to Fig. 2, made according to equation (II).

Table 2

Material	Δs , mm	experience, K ⁻¹	in the literature α , K ⁻¹
brass	600	$17.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$18 \cdot 10^{-6}$
steel	600	$11.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$11 \cdot 10^{-6}$
glass	600	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-6}$

In short, in determining the coefficient of linear expansion of various solids, comparison with the standard ensures that they meet the new material metrology standards.

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